

THE POLICY OF DIGITIZATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROCESSES AS A FACTOR IN ACCELERATING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract. The policy of digitization of socio-economic processes includes the main goals of introducing innovations in economic sectors, making public services and governance transparent, developing digital infrastructure, ensuring information security, and ensuring the convenient and easy delivery of social services to all segments of society. In our country, the policy of digitization is mainly aimed at increasing the efficiency of the economy, improving the quality of life of the population, and ensuring global competitiveness through the introduction of innovative technologies.

Keywords: digital literacy, digital technologies, "E-government", "E-commerce", digital platforms, cybersecurity.

The policy of digitization of socio-economic processes includes a set of measures aimed at accelerating the socio-economic development of the country, improving the quality of life of the population and the efficiency of public services. The policy and strategies of digitization in Uzbekistan are also one of the main directions in ensuring the socio-economic development of the country. A number of state programs have been adopted to implement this policy, including the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" program adopted in 2020, which plays an important role in accelerating the country's transition to a digital economy [1]. This goal is achieved through the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the use of digital services.

Policies and strategies for digitizing socio-economic processes are of great importance in increasing the global competitiveness of the state, improving the living conditions of the population, and developing the economy based on modern technologies. To this end, a number of works are being carried out in the following strategies and areas:

1. Digitalization of public administration. This strategy includes the development of an electronic government system (e-Government), digitization of document exchange and reduction of bureaucratic barriers, and provision of 90% of public services electronically.

2.2. Development of the digital economy. This strategy includes the automation of production processes based on ICT; the use of digital technologies in agriculture, industry, and trade; and the expansion of electronic payment systems.

3. Creating digital services for the population. In implementing this strategy, it is necessary to expand social services through information and communication technologies, introduce electronic medical services (E-Health) and online education (E-Learning) platforms, achieve widespread Internet penetration and improve the quality of mobile communications.

4. To implement the strategy for strengthening digital infrastructure, it is necessary to organize national databases and create a reliable and fast internet infrastructure.

5. Information Security. This strategy includes the development and implementation of cybersecurity standards and the development of national systems for protecting information resources.

6.6. Education and literacy. This strategy will be implemented by expanding the scope of ICT subjects in schools and universities, creating programs to increase digital literacy among the population, and training specialists in the field of ICT.

The digitalization process in Uzbekistan is aimed at modernizing the state, economy, and society through modern digital technologies.

Digital technologies are innovative solutions aimed at storing, processing, transmitting and analyzing data through digital tools and information and communication technologies (ICT). They play a significant role in increasing work efficiency, saving time and opening up new opportunities in various fields. The main types of digital technologies are:

- Information and communication technologies (ICT) (Internet and telecommunications, computer networks and cloud computing, online communication tools (e.g. videoconferencing)).
- Special software and algorithms (Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), Internet of Things (IoT), Data Analysis (Big Data)).
- Renewable technologies (renewable energy systems management technologies, sensors and drones for agriculture).
- Blockchain and cryptocurrencies (blockchain technologies used to ensure legal security and certainty, powerful and transparent electronic payment systems).

- Robotics and automation (automated systems in production, service and artificial intelligence robots).

The introduction of the above-mentioned digital technologies leads to increased work efficiency, ensuring transparency of information through digital media, economic efficiency, rapid information exchange through the Internet and databases, and the implementation of advanced innovations.

In the process of digitizing socio-economic processes in our country, a number of results have been achieved, including improving infrastructure, namely the expansion of the fiber-optic Internet system, and improving the provision of high-speed Internet networks to rural areas.

As a result of the digitalization of social services, access to public services has been created through online platforms, and licensing processes have been simplified through the "Electronic Government" system.

The following major projects were implemented to form the e-government system:

- Unified Interactive Public Services Portal (my.gov.uz);
- Open Data Portal (data.gov.uz);
- Portal for discussing draft regulatory documents (regulation.gov.uz);
- Complex of information systems "License" (license.gov.uz);
- Information system for automating the activities of "Single Window" centers (birdarcha.uz).

By 2023, the Unified Identification System of Electronic Government (id.egov.uz) will be improved, the number of users will exceed 7 million, and citizens will be able to access more than 245 information resources of state agencies through this system [5].

The Single Interactive Public Services Portal (YAIDXP, my.gov.uz) has created the opportunity to use more than 400 public services electronically without a human factor, and the demand for electronic services has increased 10 times (from 937 thousand to 9.5 million).

9.8 million services were provided through the single portal in 2020. In 2023, the number of users registered on this portal exceeded 3.6 million. Also, since the beginning of the year, users have used the portal services a total of 7.9 million times (an increase of 145 percent compared to the same period last year).

At the same time, 168 (an increase of 160%) electronic government services are being provided to the population and legal entities in the mobile

application of the Single Portal. In order to create convenience in providing public services to the population and entrepreneurs, 62 types of public services have been launched using the YAIDXP platform at 1,038 postal facilities in the regions.

The Interagency Integration Platform of e-government has been improved, and during 2022, more than 1,500 million pieces of information were exchanged between more than 120 information systems of government bodies, which will save 8.3 billion soums per month and 100 billion soums per year on paper costs alone.

At the same time, during the first quarter of 2023, more than 595 million information exchanges were carried out through the interdepartmental integration platform of the Electronic Government.

The expansion of economic opportunities has led to the active participation of local entrepreneurs in e-commerce and the strengthening of integration processes into the global IT market.

Table 1

The volume of gross added value created in the information economy and e-commerce sectors (billion soums) [6].

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Information Economy and E-Commerce Sector	6 377,8	7 732,1	8 491,9	10 777,0	16 939,5	27 755,0
Information Communication Technology (ICT) Sector	5 849,0	6 876,8	7 323,0	9 095,9	11 567,6	16 131,1
ICT Manufacturing	238,3	301,9	279,4	540,1	503,3	820,3
ICT Trade	281,6	236,2	293,3	252,3	367,8	580,8
ICT Services	5 329,1	6 338,7	6 750,3	8 303,5	10 696,4	14 730,0
Content Sector and Media	518,7	750,1	908,9	1 089,7	1 464,6	1 929,9
E-Commerce	10,1	105,2	260,0	591,4	3 907,3	9 694,0

In addition, over the past period, significant investments have been attracted to the sector to improve the republic's ICT systems and digital infrastructure. As a result, according to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the gross value added in the information and communications sector increased by more than 2.5 times in 2017-2022, reaching 16,131.1 billion soums in 2022 (Table 1).

The total length of fiber-optic communication lines in our country has increased significantly since 2017. For example, according to the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

this indicator increased almost 7 times in 2017-2022, and at the end of 2022, the total length of fiber-optic communication lines reached 170.9 thousand kilometers.

Table 2

Internet access of the population (per 100 permanent residents) [6].

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	34,5	40,4	48,8	58,4	65,8	75,0
individuals	33,2	39,1	46,9	56,2	63,3	70,6

As can be seen from the data in Table 2, the number of Internet users per 100 permanent residents has more than doubled compared to 2017, reaching 70.6. It should be noted that the country's Internet system is growing every year, which increases the effective functioning of the technological age.

By 2030, by ensuring stable high growth rates in economic sectors, it is planned to increase GDP per capita by 1.6 times and per capita income by more than \$4,000 in the next five years, creating the basis for entering the ranks of "upper-middle-income countries."

Increasing the digital literacy of the population through the introduction of ICT courses in the education system and the increase in IT training centers (IT parks).

In line with the demands of the times, our country is paying great attention to improving telecommunications infrastructure and digitizing industries and networks. This year alone, 100 software projects have been developed within the framework of digital transformation of such sectors as education, banking, finance, customs, agriculture, geology, and cadastre. More than 500 new IT companies have been established, and \$475 million in foreign direct investment has been invested in the sector.

A videoconference meeting was held on December 20, 2023, chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on priority tasks for the development of information technologies in sectors and regions and the digitalization of public administration. The meeting determined the creation of additional conditions for the development of the sector:

- IT companies will be placed in vacant buildings in the regions for free for a year;
- talented programmers will be provided with computers and equipment, with the condition of paying in installments within a year;

- companies employing more than 50 IT specialists will be reimbursed up to 15% of their annual salary costs;

- exporting enterprises will be compensated for 50% of the costs of attracting external experts and participating in international conferences.

Although our country has achieved some success in digitizing socio-economic processes, there are a number of problems and threats in this process. These include cybersecurity problems (lack of mechanisms to protect information systems), infrastructure deficiencies (problems in covering all regions with high-speed Internet), financial resource requirements (the need for large investments for the introduction of digital technologies), and most importantly, low digital literacy of the population (lack of knowledge in some communities on how to use new technologies).

The digitalization process in Uzbekistan is helping to stimulate economic growth, improve the standard of living of society, and make public administration more effective. To successfully continue this process, it is necessary to implement the following:

1. Strengthen cybersecurity and protect information systems.
2. Introduce special programs to increase the digital literacy of the population.
3. Strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors.
4. Provide high-speed Internet to all regions.

The digitalization process is an important tool for strengthening Uzbekistan's position in the global economy and achieving sustainable development.

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